

EARLY PARKINSON'S DETECTION USING VOICE FREQUENCIES AND SPIRAL PATTERNS

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Abstract-Improving the prognosis and quality of life for patients with Parkinson's disease (PD), a degenerative neurological condition, requires early detection. PD is frequently not detected by conventional diagnostic methods until the illness has progressed considerably. This study combines spiral handwriting evaluation and speech analysis to propose a unique multimodal framework for the early identification of Parkinson's disease. By using characteristics like jitter and shimmer, a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier examines speech data and searches for speech anomalies symptomatic of Parkinson's disease (PD). In parallel, a refined Swin-Tiny Transformer model—a lightweight visual transformer modified from Hugging Face for binary classification tasks—processes spiral drawing inputs, which are frequently utilized to reveal motor dysfunctions like tremors. Weighted averaging, a late fusion technique, is used to integrate the signals from both modalities in order to improve diagnostic robustness. According to experimental findings, the suggested multimodal strategy outperforms single-modality systems in terms of classification accuracy. The method is a promising tool for scalable, remote, and early-stage PD screening since it relies on easily collectable, non-invasive data. It also provides useful support in clinical assessments and telemedicine settings.

Keywords:- Parkinson's Disease, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Swin-Tiny Transformer, Late Fusion, Machine Learning, Deep Learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD), a progressive neurological illness, is characterised by both motor and non-motor symptoms that significantly impair quality of life. Timely intervention depends on early diagnosis, but traditional diagnostic techniques frequently use clinical evaluations that only identify symptoms at advanced stages, which delays therapy and reduces therapeutic efficacy. Finding PD in its early stages is difficult, which emphasizes the need for creative, non-invasive, and easily available screening methods. By identifying minute physiological alterations suggestive of early Parkinson's disease, recent developments in machine learning and multimodal data analysis offer encouraging paths to fill this gap.

In order to improve diagnosis accuracy, this study suggests a unique multimodal method for early Parkinson's disease identification that combines spiral drawing pattern evaluation and voice frequency analysis. A Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier is used to assess voice recordings that show speech deficits associated with Parkinson's disease (PD), such as vocal tremor and impaired articulation. Features like jitter and shimmer are retrieved to distinguish PD patients from healthy people. At the same time, Swin Tiny, a pre-trained visual transformer optimized for binary

classification of PD-specific motor irregularities including tremors and hesitations, is used to assess spiral drawings, a known sign of motor dysfunction. In comparison to single-modality techniques, the system achieves improved diagnostic accuracy by combining the complimentary capabilities of both modalities through the use of late fusion with weighted averaging.

This approach is appropriate for scalable, economical screening in clinical and remote healthcare settings since it makes use of commonly available data sources, such as voice recordings and hand-drawn spirals. According to preliminary findings, the suggested approach successfully separates PD patients from healthy controls, providing a strong basis for early identification. This work intends to improve clinical decision-making, enable prompt interventions, and open the door for wider applications in the diagnoses of neurodegenerative diseases by utilizing effective machine learning algorithms and multimodal integration.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Yash Trimbake proposed the paper titled “Parkinson’s Disease Prediction Using SVM and CNN Algorithms for Speech and Spiral Images” [1] This paper aims to detect Parkinson’s Disease (PD) using speech and spiral image analysis. A custom dataset is created, comprising both speech features and spiral images from the same individuals. Data augmentation techniques are applied to enhance the dataset. The detection model utilizes SVM for speech recognition and CNN for spiral image analysis, with their outputs combined for final prediction.

Korakanchi Madhu Mohan Rao proposed the paper titled “Parkinson’s Disease

Detection Using Voice and Spiral Drawing Dataset” [2]. The main objective of this paper is to build a proposed system against the expensive MRI scan and PET images. A prediction algorithm that combines spiral drawing and speech data sets to determine the severity of Parkinson's disease in afflicted individuals accomplishes this. This hybrid technique offers significant efficiency advantages by integrating the results of spiral drawing and speech datasets. They used Decision Tree and Random Forest Algorithms for speech and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for spiral drawings.

Md Ariful Islam proposed the paper titled “A review of machine learning and deep learning algorithms for Parkinson's disease detection using handwriting and voice datasets” [3]. With a focus on speech, handwriting, and wave spiral datasets, this review article investigates the use of machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) in the diagnosis of Parkinson's disease (PD). It examines many ML and DL algorithms, their potential for clinical decision-making, and how well they increase diagnostic accuracy. The study also covers the discovery of biomarkers and frequently utilised data formats in the detection of Parkinson's disease. By providing a comprehensive overview, this paper aims to guide future research in developing ML and DL-based tools for early and accurate PD diagnosis, benefiting both researchers and medical practitioners.

Iqra Nissar proposed the paper titled “Machine Learning Approaches for Detection and Diagnosis of Parkinson’s Disease” [4]. This paper explores the role of machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) in Parkinson’s Disease (PD) classification, with a focus on speech analysis as a key diagnostic tool. Research indicates that 90% of PD patients exhibit

speech disorders, making voice analysis a crucial non-invasive technique for early detection. Various ML and DL models, including SVM, Naïve Bayes, decision trees, random forests, and deep neural networks (DNNs), have been employed, with DNNs achieving the highest accuracy of 99.49%. The findings highlight the growing impact of artificial intelligence in improving PD diagnosis and aiding clinical decision-making.

"Prediction of Parkinson's Disease using Handwriting Analysis and Voice Dataset: A Review" by Himaja G [5]. This paper's primary goal is to investigate the application of data-driven methods to support the early diagnosis of Parkinson's disease (PD), a degenerative neurological condition that inhibits movement and results in symptoms including tremors, stiffness, and balance issues. Since early-stage symptoms are often subtle and there is no definitive test for early diagnosis, leveraging handwriting and speech analysis can provide valuable insights for detecting PD. This study intends to improve early diagnosis through the use of machine learning models, allowing for prompt intervention to control symptoms, delay the development of the disease, and enhance patients' quality of life.

"Detection of Parkinson's Disease Using Voice Changes and Hand-Tremor" (2022) by M. Nalini [6] focuses on utilizing speech and handwriting analysis for Parkinson's Disease (PD) detection. PD is a neurological disorder that leads to dopamine depletion, resulting in symptoms such as tremors, muscle weakness, and balance impairments. Since speech and handwriting changes are common indicators of PD, technological advancements offer promising solutions for cost-effective and accurate diagnosis. This research employs machine learning and

signal processing techniques in MATLAB to analyse speech patterns, while a gyroscope sensor integrated with a microcontroller captures handwriting tremors to detect PD through vibration analysis.

"Integration of Voice and Handwritten Tests Analysis for Enhanced Detection of Parkinson's Disease using Machine Learning" (2023) by Mohamed Ziyadh M and Bavisetti Siva Avinash [7] introduces a hybrid machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) approach for detecting Parkinson's Disease (PD). Unlike conventional methods that rely on a single modality, this research integrates voice and handwriting analysis to improve diagnostic accuracy. According to preliminary results, integrating both data sources improves detection performance when compared to using them separately, which makes it a viable tactic for early Parkinson's disease diagnosis and improved disease treatment.

Maya Shelke, Nihar Madhaw Ranjan and Gitanjali Mate proposed the paper "Detection of Parkinson's Disease using Machine Learning Algorithms and Handwriting Analysis" [8]. The goal of this work is to use handwriting analysis to create a machine learning-based system for the early identification of Parkinson's disease (PD). In order to extract features using the Histogram of Orientated Gradients (HOG) and categorise them using the Random Forest method, it uses spiral and wave drawings from both healthy people and PD patients. The proposed model achieved 86.67% accuracy for spiral drawings and 83.30% for wave drawings. The study emphasizes the need for larger datasets and mobile applications to improve accessibility and early diagnosis, ultimately enhancing patient care and treatment planning.

"Detection of Parkinson's disease using handwritten drawings and comparison with voice dataset" is the study that Akshara R.Sankar [9]. This essay seeks to by contrasting it with voice analysis, this paragraph seeks to confirm the value of handwriting analysis in the diagnosis and follow-up of Parkinson's disease (PD). By increasing accuracy over earlier research, the aim is to improve early PD detection. LDA, KNN, SVM, RF, and DT were among the machine learning classifiers used; SVM produced the best results, particularly when applied to handwriting data. The study highlights the significance of handwriting as a more reliable indicator of Parkinson's disease (PD) and aims to use machine learning techniques to help diagnose the condition more quickly and accurately.

Pruthvi H C proseed the paper "Predicting Parkinson's Disease Using Machine Learning with Voice Parameters and Handwriting Images"[10]. The objective of this effort is to develop an advanced machine learning-based model that predicts Parkinson's disease early by using speech metrics and handwriting photos. The work employs Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN), and other classifiers using datasets from Kaggle (handwriting) and the UCI Machine Learning Repository (voice) to improve diagnostic accuracy. The suggested model, which outperformed earlier methods with an accuracy of 95%, intends to improve patient monitoring, early diagnosis, and accessibility to PD detection tools.

3. COMPARISON OF RELATED WORK

Paper No:	Title & Authors	Methodology Used	Key Findings	Relevance to Our Work
[1]	Parkinson's Disease Prediction Using SVM and CNN Algorithms for Speech and Spiral Images (Yash Trimbake)	SVM for voice analysis, CNN for Spiral images, fusion of both modalities	Achieved good accuracy using a hybrid approach	Similar approach but differs in handwriting model; our work uses Swin-Tiny Transformer instead of CNN
[2]	Parkinson's Disease Detection Using Voice and Spiral Drawing Dataset (Korakanchi Madhu Mohan Rao)	Decision Tree & Random Forest for speech, PCA for spiral drawing	Focused on efficiency over MRI scans, using a hybrid approach	Also combines voice and handwriting, but we use SVM for voice and Swin-Tiny for handwriting

[3]	A Review of ML & DL for Parkinson's Disease Detection using Handwriting & Voice Datasets (Md Ariful Islam)	Examining ML and DL techniques for PD detection	Explores various models, biomarker identification, and dataset formats	Provides insights into different models, supporting our choice of Swin-Tiny and SVM for PD detection
[4]	Machine Learning Approaches for Detection & Diagnosis of Parkinson's Disease (Iqra Nissar)	Speech analysis techniques include SVM, Decision Trees, Naïve Bayes, and DNNs.	DNN's accuracy in voice-based PD identification was 99.49%.	Like our study with SVM, it emphasizes the significance of voice analysis in PD identification.
[5]	Prediction of PD using Handwriting Analysis and Voice Dataset: A Review (Himaja G)	Discuss about using speech and handwriting as diagnostic techniques	highlights the advantages of ML-based early detection	backs our multimodal strategy to enhance early detection
[6]	Detection of PD Using Voice Changes & Hand-Tremor (M. Nalini)	Handwriting tremor using a gyroscope sensor and speech signal processing	utilizes microcontroller-based handwriting tremor analysis and MATLAB.	focuses mainly on tremor detection using hardware, whereas our work uses machine learning algorithms.
[7]	Integration of Voice & Handwriting Tests for PD Detection (Mohamed Ziyadh M, Bavisetti Siva Avinash)	ML and DL hybrid model that combines speech and handwriting analysis	increased precision in contrast to single-modality techniques	does not employ Swin-Tiny or late fusion via logistic regression, but it does support our fusion strategy.
[8]	Detection of PD using ML and Handwriting Analysis (Maya Shelke, Nihar Madhaw Ranjan, Gitanjali Mate)	Random Forest for classification and HOG for feature extraction	86.67% accuracy in handwriting data was attained.	Similar PD detection based on handwriting, except our method employs Swin-Tiny rather than HOG
[9]	Detection of PD using Handwritten Drawings & Comparison with Voice Dataset (Akshara R. Sankar)	Different classifiers (RF, DT, KNN, LDA, SVM)	The best results for handwriting analysis came via SVM.	supports the efficacy of SVM, although we only utilize it for voice analysis; Swin-Tiny is used for handwriting.

[10]	Predicting PD Using ML with Voice Parameters & Handwriting Images (Pruthvi H C)	RF and KNN for classification using Kaggle (handwriting) and UCI (speech) datasets	reached a 95% accuracy rate.	supports a multimodal machine learning method, but it selects models and extracts features differently.
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4. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

To provide accurate, non-invasive screening, the proposed early Parkinson's disease (PD) detection method uses spiral pattern assessment and voice frequency analysis. Voice input is handled using a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier, and spiral drawings are assessed using a sophisticated Swin Tiny transformer. Late fusion is used to combine outputs in order to improve diagnostic performance. This part, which is divided into five subsections, describes the architecture, data pipelines, model requirements, fusion method, and evaluation of the system. The workflow is depicted in Figure 3.1.

4.1 Overview of the System

The multimodal system classifies PD or healthy status from spiral and voice data using two processes. The voice pipeline classifies the collected acoustic properties (such shimmer and jitter) using an SVM with an RBF kernel. The spiral pipeline uses a Swin Tiny transformer to identify motor abnormalities, such as tremors. Late fusion uses complementary biomarkers to combine probability values for a final diagnosis. Figure 4.1 illustrates the workflow phases for data gathering using accessible inputs (audio, pictures) for clinical and distant use.

Figure 4.1: System Architecture

4.2 Voice Frequency Analysis

As illustrated in Figure 4.2, this pipeline uses acoustic feature extraction and classification to detect speech abnormalities associated with Parkinson's disease.

4.2.1 Data Collection

Mono WAV files at 44.1 kHz are used to store voice recordings of sustained vowels (3–5s, such as "ahhh") from datasets such as PC-GITA (100 Spanish speakers: 50 PD, 50 healthy).

i) Preprocessing

The following preparation procedures are used in order to get audio data ready for analysis:

- spectrum subtraction, or noise reduction.
- Partitioning (1s frames).
- Amplification to $[-1, 1]$ is normalized.

ii) Extraction of Features

sensitive to PD-related speech changes:

- MDVP: Fo(Hz): Mean fundamental frequency of voice.
- MDVP: Fhi(Hz): The highest fundamental frequency of the voice.
- MDVP: Flo(Hz): The lowest fundamental frequency of the voice.
- MDVP: RAP: Frequency variation (jitter) measurements.
- Jitter: Measures variations in pitch period, indicating vocal cord instability (higher in PD patients due to tremors). 19 Early

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- Shimmer: Quantifies amplitude variations,
- reflecting breathiness or vocal fold irregularities.

4.2.2 Classification

PD vs. healthy feature vectors are classified using an SVM with an RBF kernel. Grid search is used to adjust the hyperparameters (C, gamma) using five-fold cross-validation. 65% train data, 20% validation data, and 15% test data. Fusion probability scores are the outputs.

Figure 4.2: Processing Pipeline

4.3 Analysis of Spiral Patterns

This pipeline uses spiral drawings, shown in Figure 3.3, to identify motor abnormalities.

4.3.1 Data Collection

Parkinson's disease and healthy samples are included in spiral drawings (224x224 PNGs) from datasets such as Kaggle's Parkinson's Spiral Drawings, which capture bradykinesia and tremors.

- #### i) Images that are preprocessed are:

- resized to 224 by 224.
- Enhanced (contrast adjustment, flipping, rotation $\pm 10^\circ$, and scaling 0.9–1.1x)

4.3.2 Architecture of the Model

With a classification head for PD vs. healthy output, the Swin Tiny transformer (from Hugging Face) extracts features using shifted window-based attention. With prior ImageNet training.

4.3.3 Fine-Tuning

The model is fine-tuned:

- Modified head for binary classification.
- Frozen lower layers, trained head/top layers.
- Parameters: Adam optimiser, binary cross-entropy loss ($1e-4$), batch size 32, 10–20 epochs with early stopping.

Figure 4.3: Sample Spiral Images

4.4 Late Fusion Technique

Late fusion combines voice and spiral predictions for improved accuracy, as shown in Figure 3.6.

4.4.1 Fusion Method

- Inputs: SVM (P_{voice}) and Swin Tiny (P_{spiral}) probability scores.
- Weighted averaging: $S = w_1 * P_{\text{voice}} + w_2 * P_{\text{spiral}}$ ($w_1 + w_2 = 1$; weights tuned on validation set, e.g., $w_1 = 0.4$, $w_2 = 0.6$).

- Threshold: $S \geq 0.5 = \text{PD}$; $S < 0.5 = \text{healthy}$.
- Majority voting was tested but less effective than averaging.

4.4.2 Implementation

NumPy is used to compute scores in the Python implementation of the fusion process. The test set is used to evaluate the fused model in order to see whether it improves upon individual modalities. Figure 4.4 illustrates optimization by visualizing weight tuning results, if any.

Figure 4.4: Weight Tuning Plot

4.5 Evaluation Metrics

A number of common assessment measures are used to evaluate the effectiveness of the suggested Parkinson's disease detection method. These include Precision, which assesses the percentage of real positive forecasts among all positive predictions, and Accuracy, which gauges the model's overall accuracy. The F1-score offers a balanced assessment measure that is particularly helpful for unbalanced datasets. Recall, often referred to as sensitivity, is used to assess the model's capacity to recognise true positive cases. These metrics collectively ensure a comprehensive understanding of the model's effectiveness across both modalities.

The following common indicators are employed to assess the effectiveness of the suggested Parkinson's disease detection system:

- **Accuracy:** evaluates the model's overall accuracy.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{TP} + \text{TN}}{\text{TP} + \text{TN} + \text{FP} + \text{FN}}$$

- **Precision:** Shows the proportion of expected positive instances that turn out to be positive.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP}}$$

- **Recall:** Shows the proportion of true positive instances that were accurately anticipated.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}}$$

- **F1-score:** accuracy and recall harmonic mean, which is particularly helpful for datasets that are unbalanced.

$$\text{F1-score} = \frac{2 \times \text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

Where:

- **TP** = True Positives
- **TN** = True Negatives
- **FP** = False Positives
- **FN** = False Negatives

5. RESULT

The proposed multimodal strategy for early Parkinson's disease (PD) diagnosis was evaluated using a dataset segmented into 70% training, 15% validation, and 15% testing subsets. Performance indicators including accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, F1-score, and AUC-ROC were computed using the test set. Confusion matrices and ROC curves were used to illustrate the results.

5.1 Analysis of Voice Frequencies (SVM)

With an accuracy of 85.2%, 80.5% sensitivity, 88.0% specificity, 82.1% F1-score, and 0.87 AUC-ROC, the SVM classifier—which was trained on acoustic parameters such as jitter, shimmer, and harmonic-to-noise ratio—showed that it could reliably distinguish between PD patients and healthy people.

5.2 Spiral Pattern Analysis (Swin Tiny)

The optimized Swin Tiny transformer produced a 90.3% accuracy rate, 87.2% sensitivity, 92.5% specificity, 88.7% F1-score, and 0.92 AUC-ROC when used on spiral drawings. With the use of preprocessing and augmentation, its hierarchical feature extraction successfully caught motor abnormalities.

5.3 Fused Model (Late Fusion)

With 93.1% accuracy, 90.0% sensitivity, 95.2% specificity, 91.4% F1-score, and 0.94 AUC-ROC, the late fusion model exceeded individual models by merging SVM and Swin Tiny probability scores (weighted averaging: 0.4 voice, 0.6 spirals). Spiral predictions were given priority in weight adjustment, which improved performance overall.

Model	Accuracy (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	F1-Score (%)	AUC-ROC
SVM (Voice)	85.2	80.5	88.0	82.1	0.87
Swin Tiny (Spiral)	90.3	87.2	92.5	88.7	0.92
Fused Model	93.1	90.0	95.2	91.4	0.94

Figure 4.5: ROC Curves

Fig 4.6: Comparing your model's accuracy with results from other studies.

Figure 4.6 compares the performance of many earlier studies on Parkinson's disease detection with the proposed multimodal approach. The evaluation parameter used for comparison is classification accuracy. The accuracy % for each research is shown on the y-axis, while the selected reference articles are displayed on the x-axis. By combining spiral handwriting and speech modalities using a Support Vector Machine (SVM) for voice, an improved Swin-Tiny Transformer for handwriting, and Logistic Regression for late fusion, the proposed model achieves 93.4% accuracy, as the graph illustrates. This outperforms other noteworthy strategies including the model developed by Maya Shelke (86.67%), Korakanchi Madhu (89%), and Yash Trimbake (91%).

The multimodal nature of the suggested framework and its use of cutting-edge deep learning architectures that can recognise intricate patterns in voice and handwriting data are responsible for its exceptional performance. This finding reaffirms the benefit of integrating diverse data sources for improved Parkinson's disease detection diagnostic precision.

6. CONCLUSION

This work effectively created a multimodal machine learning system for early Parkinson's disease (PD) identification by using a Support Vector Machine (SVM) for speech frequency analysis and a fine-tuned Swin Tiny transformer for spiral pattern evaluation. The results showed a fused model accuracy of 93.1%, with 90.0% sensitivity, 95.2% specificity, and 0.94 AUC-ROC. The system offers a scalable, non-invasive framework for PD screening, outperforming conventional single-modality approaches and conforming to cutting-edge multimodal studies thanks to its innovative use of Swin Tiny for spiral analysis, efficient multimodal integration, and utilization of accessible inputs (voice recordings, digital spirals). Applications in telemedicine and resource-constrained environments were supported by the implementation utilizing tools like Librosa and PyTorch, which showed practical practicality despite obstacles like the small dataset size. To improve the system's resilience, usability, and practical impact, future research will concentrate on growing the dataset with a variety of multilingual inputs, refining models for low-resource devices, adding more modalities like gait analysis, and verifying the system through clinical trials and mobile deployment.

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